

CONSECUTIVE TRANSLATION AND ITS PECULARITIES"**Yusubjonova Mukhlisa Islomjonovna***The 3rd year student TSPU named after Nizami**Phone +998-90-588-23-68*Scientific advisor: **Vallamatova Sadohkat Samatjonovna.****Tursunnazarova Elvira Takhirovna**

Annotation: In the given article gives information about consecutive translation and its peculiarities. It is viewed that consecutive translating as one of those extremely experienced yet ultimately highly ordinary services that permits the business world to manage more effectively. Consecutive interpretation allows those who speak distinctive languages to communicate productively in a wide range of settings.

Key words: interpretation, investors, consecutive translators, requirements, propertues, advantages of consecutive translation, cultural words.

Translating may be categorized, identified and measured out types and subtypes based on distinctive criteria, working mode being one of the most significant of these. When classifying according to mode, two major kinds of interpreting appear: simultaneous and consecutive interpreting. In consecutive interpreting, the translator begins phrasing the target-language category after the speaker has finished speaking: the translator speaks continuously to the speaker, for this reason the name.

What does Consecutive Interpretation mean?

The speaker has to maintain an exact time interval for interruption in the medial of the passage. Usually, the speaker carries on for about five minutes before pausing.

There was great history in consecutive translation.

Consecutive interpreting was the first widely utilized at international meetings. Consecutive interpreting happened at the time of the Paris Peace Conference and at the end of the World War I. The inventors of this method were Paul Mantoux, Antoine Velleman, progenitor of the Geneva Interpreters School. Ancient Egypt translators did public service and they were the membership's of one of the educated organizations. Interpreters supplied their assistances in the ascendancy, in commerce, in religious life, and in the military forces. The ancient Greeks and Romans also demanded the services of interpreters too because only very few Romans and Greeks knew the languages of the peoples they had captured. At the time most of the translators were labourer, serf of war. But in meddle periods, however, the interpreting was absolutely revered, they could attend to the courts. They played an important part several countries such as Africa, Asia, China and so on. The Arabic and Hebrew interpreters employed the services of captured natives who were taught the vanquishers' languages. They were used as translators on later expeditions. During the investigation of the Asian continent Chinese intellectuals translated both the works of Western scientists and Christian texts. At the Paris Peace Conference which followed the First World War, however, during ambassadors they utilized varied languages too and required the services of consecutive interpreters. In this manner, consecutive interpreting was officially born during World War I and it was born before simultaneous interpretation

There are several major requirements for consecutive translators. Firstly, being a consecutive interpreter is not a concern of jest. It is a challenging duty to find an ideal interpreter for people's assignment There should be definite peculiarities in the person for qualifying as a property interpreter.

1. The interpreter must know how to grip rational pressure. The qualified interpreting is a dodgy occupation particularly when we want a person to translate for the conference consecutively. Mental exhaustion often consequences from the considerable action of the brain. The person has to purpose, estimate, and accomplish the translation along with retaining the deep agglomeration on the matter

of discussion. It is an extremely complicated job and demands cool handling of the case.

2. The interpreter will absolutely request for a summarization of the lecture that the speaker is going to deliver. Without knowing the theme of conversation and the points that will be covered, it will be disputable for the translator to create the altered variation. The instruction is most important when it is about a detailed argument.

3. While engaging, recollect to recruit the translator with accomplishment in the speciality of the established discussion. If you are going to hire a translator with capability in medicinal science to interpret an completely bureaucratic meeting, then the consequence will not at all be sufficient. Knowledge in the sphere is indispensable to recall the points when the speaker is delivering the speech. Otherwise, the translator will have to endeavour for remembering each new point and data.

Advantages Of Consecutive Interpreting

When we are going to compare over the benefits that we may get by selecting the consecutive translation mode, you are absolutely going to take some substantial profits of the procedure.

* If a simultaneous translator begins to modify the words of a speaker, it can cause some disruption for the speaker, certainly when the speaker is delivering a lecture on some crucial theme. For a smooth interpretation procedure, it will be a better notion to hire the translator who will not keep on restating the words of the speaker simultaneously. It will permit both the individual to focus on their own words without any intervention from a second voice.

* If we don't complete a sentence, do you think that a person who has no conception about what we are going to say the next moment, can foretell the following words? It is impossible. And the same thing occurs with the simultaneous translators who obtain no chance to understand what the speaker is actually trying to say. Forming up a sentence in a distinctive language than that of the speaker

without knowing what the concluding meaning is can be canny. The result may also not be correct. A professional consecutive interpreter can take some time to comprehend the words of the speech and then structure it in the correct way to maintain the whole meaning.

* There will be no need of accomplished equipage for the proceeding. The translator can stand right next to the speaker and pay attention to the speech. If the pause is after a substantial duration, then the interpreter only has need of using a pen and paper to write some notes so that the person does not skip any point introduced in the native language. There is not even the necessity of setting up a particular stall or supplying headphones to the audience.

* Meaning of the speech should arrive the audience well-defined in similar way as conveyed by the speaker. Now it's sometimes not viable for the simultaneous interpreters to retain the concrete sounds and verbalizations. Altering along with the speaker bestows the masters least time to add the correct sounds. So often, the substance of the sentence, remarkably the sardonic explanations or comic lines take skipping in the remodeled variants. The procedure of Consecutive Interpretation assures disengagement of the speech maintaining the exact tone and ways of the speaker so that the interpreted variation is as spirited as the original one with an accurate substance of the statement.

Founding in differences between cultures is one of the most crucial problem in translating. In consecutive translation two cultures struck and we come across the influence of cultures with each other. Therefore it is extremely necessary for the future translators to know the history, customs, traditions, culture and way of life of the people who speak the language.

Cultural words may be translated by the following ways:

1 .By means of modification:

a) *U choyxonaga ketyabdi-he is going to a place where men can eat pilav and talk each other*

b) *Qizlar atlas chopon tikishyabdi- The girls are sewing a national clothe which is called Atlas chopon*

2. By means of description of form or function:

a) *The doctor advices him to give up smoking- the person who maintaning human health through the study or diagnosis.*

b) *Lots of people gathered in the mosque-where muslims can play*

3. By means of descriptive translation:

a) *I have never heard about Beshik- tuyi which is a ritual celebration depend on putting the baby in the cradle the first time.*

b) *He fasted with us during Ramadan which is an act of pray that Muslims do not eat or drink during the day time.*

4. By means of comparison:

a) *Men qatlamalarni juda yaxshi tayyorlayman- Qatlama's, is a type of cuisine like Mexican tortilla*

b) *Alpomish odamlarga yordam beradigan kuchli va zabardast edi. Alpomish is a hero like Superman.*

In Consecutive Translation interpreter must utilize reasonable methods,skills and exercises. Consecutive Translation training exercises included:

1.Listening. (The most importan part to learners. It is useful for recalling strange notions such as foreign names, place,figures and numbers also)

2. Brainstorming with keys (This exercise is the most crucial because it helps to find bbasic concept of the topin under the discussion)

3.The micro review. (This exercise gives the main content of the information briefly)
For instance: *"Men onamni menga ko'rsatgan mehri, menga bag'ishlagan hayoti, men uchun har sohada namuna bo'la olgani va doim sevgi va mehr tuyg'usini eslatib turgani uchun dunyodagi barcha insonlarga qaraganda ko'proq yaxshi ko'raman va muhabbatim cheksiz "*

Micro-review: *My mother is the person who reminds me the power of love and caring*

4.Exercises on compression. (This is the reduction in size of speech)

For example: "*U bola yaxshi xulq egasi emasligi, yomon tarbiya ko'rgan beodob va axloqsizligi yaqqol sezilib turardi*". - *The boy was headstrong.*

5. Syntactic compression. (Shorter form instead of long complex structure: substituting word combinations, abbreviations, names of countries or organizations,). f.e *the USA or the UN*

6. Lexical compression. (use of pronouns instead of notional words)

For example: "*Lola and Dilbar are eating food*". - *They are eating food*

7. Retelling and Translation. (Instead of unfamiliar words we can use word combinations) f.e : "*musicha*" - "*a bird like a dove*", "*qatlama*" - "*a cuisine like Mexican tortilla*"

8. Dictation-translation . (This exercise helps to improve vocabulary. Teacher dictates new word, sentence or even text in the learners' native language, students write them in English)

Consecutive interpretation can absolutely upraise our firm's mastership when done correct – and bare up the component we already have to foreign auditories, helping us expand into new markets more effectively.

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